

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-288-IE-1% 05 RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230412
Vial:	98	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 288
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	273.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 273.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired: 4/12/2023 11:31:15 AM CST			
Date Processed: 4/12/2023 2:52:20 PM CST			

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	20.391	671682	13.04	24521
2	21.718	1921483	37.30	63358
3	23.601	635992	12.34	19856
4	24.503	1922697	37.32	57279

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-289-IE-1% 05 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230412
Vial:	99	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 289
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	273.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 273.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/12/2023 12:01:56 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 2:54:00 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	20.414	63808	1.90	2304
2	21.797	2755	0.08	221
3	23.596	2561	0.08	240
4	24.395	3282696	97.94	90497